

Impact of Different Energy Levels of Virtual Monoenergetic Reconstructions on Radiomic Features Stability in Organic Phantom Imaging Using Photon-Counting CT

Supplementary Material

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Abbreviations

ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
CCC	Concordance Correlation Coefficient
CI	Confidence Interval
CP	Coverage Probability
CT	Computed Tomography
CV	Coefficient of Variation
EMS	Expected Mean Square
ICC	Intraclass Correlation Coefficient
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
keV	Kilo-Electron-Volt
kV	Kilovolt
LoA	Limits of Agreement
mAs	Milliamperere second
MS	Mean Square
MSD	Mean Squared Deviation
No	Number
PCCT	Photon-Counting Computed Tomography
PER	Polyenergetic Reconstruction
R^2	Coefficient of Determination of Linear Regression
SEM	Standard Error of Measurement
SS	Sum of Squares
TDI	Total Deviation Index
VMER	Virtual Monoenergetic Reconstruction

Theoretical Basis for Statistical Analysis

Precision

Precision refers to the closeness of repeated measurements taken under the same conditions [1]. It describes the degree to which independent measurements of the same subject agree when using the same measuring method and procedure [2] – in this context, the term ‘subject’ is used to refer to the entity on which the measurements are taken. Precision does not indicate the repeatability of a measurement, but rather the sturdiness of the measuring instrument or its readings while measuring. According to ASTM E177 [3], precision is defined as “the closeness of agreement between independent test results obtained under stipulated conditions.” It is influenced solely by the distribution of random errors and does not relate to the true or accepted reference value [4]. A method is considered perfectly precise if it has no measurement error [5].

Accuracy

Accuracy refers to the closeness of a measured value to the true value of the subject [2] and reflects the quality of the measurement. It can be defined as the degree of closeness to an expected or true value and is not the same as precision [4]. Since accuracy is independent of precision, a measurement may be precise but inaccurate or it may be accurate but not precise. Achieving high accuracy generally requires high precision, though they are distinct concepts [2]. This becomes clearer when considering the definition provided by ISO 3534-2 [6] which states that accuracy is composed of two criteria, the precision and the trueness. Trueness, in this context, refers to the closeness of the measured value to the accepted reference value [4]. It’s important to note that accuracy is only meaningful when there is an objective reference for the ‘true’ value, such as an accepted reference value or a measurement from a gold-standard method (the measurement of a gold-standard method corresponds as closely as possible to the true value [7]). In the absence of such a reference, the term ‘accuracy’ is not applicable [1].

Agreement

Agreement between measurements refers to the extent to which measurements coincide and the degree of their differences [8] and is a characteristic of the measurement method(s) involved [9]. It is not influenced by the population being measured, unless there is a bias, or measurement precision varies depending on the true value being measured [9]. When assessing agreement, the focus is on the absolute magnitude of measurement error. Therefore, variability between subjects or the distribution of the measured values within the population is not relevant [8]. Agreement between two measurements can be assessed visually by plotting the observed values, with one set on the x-axis and the other on the y-axis, representing points with corresponding x and y components. Agreement is observed when the paired data points align closely with the identity line, characterized by a straight line with no intercept and a slope of one [10].

Choudhary and Nagaraja [5] define agreement mathematically by considering paired measurements, X and Y , taken from randomly chosen subjects from a population. These pairs, (X, Y) , are treated as measurements from the same subjects, with either different methods or repeated measures of the same method. It is assumed that the joint distribution of X and Y follows a continuous bivariate distribution with means (μ_x, μ_y) , variances (σ_x^2, σ_y^2) and covariance σ_{yx} . If $D = Y - X$ denotes the difference in the measurements, then it follows a

continuous distribution with mean $\mu_d = \mu_y - \mu_x$ and variance $\sigma_d^2 = \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_x^2 - 2\sigma_{yx} = \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_x^2 - 2\rho\sigma_y\sigma_x$, where ρ is the Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Agreement between two methods refers to closeness between their measurements. The methods have perfect agreement in the ideal case when $P(Y = X) = 1$. In this case, the bivariate distribution of (X, Y) is concentrated on the line of equality – the 45° line, causing the distribution of the difference to be degenerate at zero. This will be reflected in the scatterplot of Y versus X if all (X, Y) values fall on the line of equality. Accordingly, perfect agreement corresponds to any of the following two equivalent conditions [5]:

- 1) $\{\mu_y = \mu_x, \sigma_y^2 = \sigma_x^2, \rho = 1\}$ that is, the methods have equal means, equal variances, and perfect linear correlation, or
- 2) $\{\mu_d = 0, \sigma_d^2 = 0\}$, that is, the difference has zero mean and zero variance.

However, it is unlikely that this ideal condition can be fully realized in practice, and some degree of deviation from perfect agreement is inevitable. While the conditions outlined above provide the mathematical definition of agreement, a certain level of disagreement is acceptable in real-world scenarios. The deviation from this ideal condition is quantified by agreement measures, which are functions of parameters of the bivariate distribution [5].

Agreement can be assessed using various measures, which are categorized into absolute and relative indices [10]. Absolute indices include:

- **Mean Squared Deviation (MSD):** This index evaluates an aggregated deviation from the identity line. $MSD = 0$ denotes perfect agreement and small values implying good agreement. However, it is not easy to interpret [5, 10].
- **Total Deviation Index (TDI):** This index is a nonnegative measure of agreement, where small values indicate high and large values suggest poor agreement. When $TDI(p) = 0$ for all p , the methods demonstrate perfect agreement. This index is sensitive to non-normality in the data [5].
- **Coverage Probability (CP):** This index represents the proportion of the population of D that falls within the margin $\pm \delta$. It ranges from zero to one, with larger values indicating higher agreement between the methods. When $CP(\delta) = 1$ for all δ , the measurements exhibit perfect agreement. This index is sensitive to non-normality in the data [5].
- **Limits of Agreement (LoA):** This index defines the interval $(\mu_d - 1.96 \sigma_d, \mu_d + 1.96 \sigma_d)$, which covers the middle 95% of the population of D as a measure of agreement. The endpoints of this interval correspond to the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of D . If the limits of agreement fall within a specified margin $\pm \delta$, the measurements are considered to have sufficient agreement for interchangeable use. This index is also sensitive to non-normality in the data [5].

The relative index is the **Concordance Correlation Coefficient (CCC)**, which is robust to moderate deviations from normality [10] and provides a measure of agreement that accounts for both precision (degree of scatter) and accuracy (degree of systematic location and scale shifts) [11].

Repeatability

Repeatability refers to the degree of agreement between independent measurements obtained using the same method on identical subjects under identical conditions [12]. According to ASTM E177 [3], repeatability is defined as the “precision under repeatability conditions” and the repeatability conditions is defined as the “conditions where independent

test results are obtained with the same method on identical test items in the same laboratory by the same operator using the same equipment within short intervals of time”.

In a repeatability study, at least two measurements must be taken per subject under identical conditions [9]. During this process, the true underlying values of the subjects remain unchanged, and neither the accuracy nor the precision of the method is affected. Consequently, any variation in repeated measurements arises solely from inherent errors within the measurement process itself. Therefore, repeatability essentially quantifies the measurement errors of a method, offering insight into its consistency. Since repeatability reflects a method's ability to agree with itself, it is crucial to evaluate it. Without good repeatability, a method cannot be expected to consistently agree with other methods or produce stable results across different tests [5].

Reproducibility

Reproducibility refers to the degree of agreement between independent measurements obtained using the same method on identical subjects, but under different conditions. These conditions may include variations in instruments, laboratories, or measurement instruments [5, 9, 12]. According to ASTM E177 [3], reproducibility is defined as the “precision under reproducibility conditions” and the reproducibility conditions is defined as the “conditions where test results are obtained with the same method on identical test items in different laboratories with different operators using different equipment”.

Reproducibility can also involve measuring subjects over time, during which their true values may change. In some cases, if the interest is focused on a fixed set of specified conditions and the true value of subjects does not change, the ‘condition’ may be treated as a fixed effect rather than a random one. This means that the reproducibility simply becomes a synonym for **agreement** between the measurements [9].

Reproducibility is not a property of the measurement itself, but rather the variability observed when different raters measure the same subjects, known as inter-rater variability [12]. Unlike repeatability, which quantifies the measurement errors of a method under consistent conditions, reproducibility accounts for potential systematic errors (biases) and differences in the variance of measurement errors across different raters [9]. It is important to note that if repeatability has not been found as acceptable, any assessment of reproducibility is likely to be unreliable [7].

Mean Squared Deviation

Keeping the mathematical model of Choudhary and Nagaraja in mind, the Mean squared deviation (MSD), ε^2 , defined as follows and evaluates an aggregated deviation from the identity line, $MSD = E(Y - X)^2 = E(D)^2$. Here, $E(\cdot)$ is the expected value. It can be expressed as follows [5, 10]:

$$MSD = \varepsilon^2 = \mu_d^2 + \sigma_d^2 = (\mu_y - \mu_x)^2 + \rho_y^2 + \sigma_x^2 - 2\sigma_{yx}$$

The MSD is not an easy index to interpret. The TDI and CP as well as LoA are giving some meaningful interpretation on this index. The CCC is the standardization of the MSD [10].

Concordance Correlation Coefficient

The CCC is a dimensionless index used to assess the agreement between two sets of measurements by evaluating the deviation from the 45° line through the origin (the concordance line) [13]. It ranges from -1 to 1 and shares a similar sign with the Pearson's

Correlation Coefficient [5]. Before delving further into the CCC, let's first introduce two important coefficients:

Accuracy Coefficient

The accuracy coefficient measures the closeness of the marginal distributions of X and Y, where 1 signifies equal means and variances, and 0 indicates that the absolute difference in means and/or variance approach infinity, is defined as follows [10]:

$$\chi_a = \frac{2}{v^2 + \varpi + \frac{1}{\varpi}}$$

It can be broken down into measures of location and/or scale shifts, where the location shift is denoted with v , and the scale shift is denoted with ϖ , which are defined as follows [10]:

$$v = \frac{\mu_y - \mu_x}{\sqrt{\sigma_y \sigma_x}}$$

$$\varpi = \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_x} \text{ or } \frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_y}$$

Precision Coefficient

Here, the precision coefficient is the correlation coefficient (ρ) between X and Y, which measures how tightly concentrated the bivariate distribution is around a straight line [5, 10]:

$$\rho = \frac{\sigma_{yx}}{\sigma_y \sigma_x}$$

Concordance Correlation Coefficient

The CCC, ρ_c , is likely the most widely used index among statisticians for assessing agreement [10]. It rescales the MSD so that the resulting values of CCC lie within the range of -1 to 1. This is done using the following formula [5, 10]:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_c &= 1 - \frac{MSD}{MSD_0} = 1 - \frac{\varepsilon^2}{\varepsilon_{\rho=0}^2} \\ &= 1 - \frac{(\mu_y - \mu_x)^2 + \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_x^2 - 2\sigma_{yx}}{(\mu_y - \mu_x)^2 + \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_x^2} \\ &= \frac{2\sigma_{yx}}{(\mu_y - \mu_x)^2 + \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_x^2} \\ &= \frac{2\rho\sigma_y\sigma_x}{(\mu_y - \mu_x)^2 + \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_x^2} \\ &= \rho \frac{2}{\frac{(\mu_y - \mu_x)^2}{\sigma_y\sigma_x} + \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_x} + \frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_y}} \\ &= \rho\chi_a \end{aligned}$$

Here, MSD_0 represents the MSD value assuming X and Y are independent. Under the assumption of independence, the covariance between X and Y, denoted as σ_{yx} , is zero [5, 10].

The formula shows that CCC is the product of Accuracy and Precision Coefficients. When it is equal to 1 indicates that each pair of readings is in perfect agreement in the population while

0 indicates no correlation, and -1 means that each pair of readings is in perfect reversed agreement in the population [5, 10]. In contrast to TDI, CP and LoA, the CCC and Accuracy and Precision Coefficient estimates are in general quite robust against moderate deviation from normality [10].

Reliability

Reliability refers to the proportion of the total variance that can be attributed to true differences in the measured values. It is often expressed as the ratio of the variance of true values (denoted as σ_{true}^2) to the total variance of the observed measurements. This ratio is known as the reliability coefficient (R) and can be calculated using the following formula [1, 14]:

$$R = \frac{\sigma_{true}^2}{\sigma_{observed}^2}$$

The difference between the true value and the observed measurements is referred to as measurement error [14]. This error can consist of two components, depending on the study: random error and systematic error (bias) [1]. Systematic error includes both constant error and bias. Constant error affects all measurements equally, while bias is a type of systematic error that affects certain measurements more than others. In contrast, random error stems from unpredictable, chance-related factors [15]. Based on this, the formula can be expressed as follows:

$$R = \frac{\sigma_{true}^2}{\sigma_{true}^2 + \sigma_{error}^2} = \frac{\sigma_{true}^2}{\sigma_{true}^2 + \sigma_{systematic\ error}^2 + \sigma_{random\ error}^2}$$

As measurement values approach the true value, reliability increases, so that with zero error, perfect reliability will be achieved, and the coefficient will reach 1.0. Conversely, as error increases, reliability diminishes, causing the coefficient to approach 0 [14]. Unfortunately, reliability cannot be directly calculated using this the formula above because true values cannot be measured. Instead, reliability must be estimated indirectly through the statistical concept of variance [14, 16]. To do this, the appropriate variances must be estimated from the expected mean squares in analysis of variance (ANOVA) [15]. Therefore, reliability is influenced by both the magnitude of measurement errors and the variability of true values within the population being measured [9]. When data come from a heterogeneous sample, i.e. there is high between-subjects variance, reliability will likely appear to be high. It is important to understand that reliability should not be viewed as an inherent property of a specific measurement instrument. Rather, every instrument will demonstrate a certain degree of reliability when applied to particular populations under specific conditions [14].

A key caution when estimating reliability is that the hypothesis tests are not designed to assess the reliability. These tests primarily focus on identifying systematic differences between group means, but they do not consider individual variability or measurement errors, both of which are crucial factors that influence reliability. Therefore, relying solely on hypothesis tests to estimate reliability is insufficient. To obtain a more accurate assessment of reliability, they should be complemented by other methods that specifically address individual differences of measurements [14].

There are generally two types of reliability: relative and absolute. Relative reliability refers to the extent to which individuals retain their rank or position in a sample across repeated measurements. Absolute reliability, on the other hand, pertains to the degree of variation in repeated measurements for each individual, i.e. the less they vary, the higher the reliability [14, 17]. For continuous data, reliability is commonly estimated using the intraclass correlation

coefficient (ICC) and the standard error of measurement (SEM). While the ICC is a unitless, relative measure of reliability, the SEM provides a measure of absolute reliability and is expressed in the same units as the original measurements [14, 15].

Reliability is a context-dependent concept that is difficult to interpret as a dimensionless quantity. Determining what constitutes ‘sufficiently high reliability’ is often subjective [9], and there is no universal minimum acceptable level that applies to all measures, as it varies depending on the study design, the measurement tool used, and the characteristics of the subjects involved. The decision on whether a measurement method is reliable or not is inherently open to interpretation and requires evaluating whether the level of measurement error is acceptable for the study’s objectives. Since there are no firm rules for making this decision, comparisons across different studies are challenging, except in very general terms [14]. Moreover, the reliability of a method is not solely determined by the size of measurement errors but also by the heterogeneity of true values within the population being measured. Thus, while agreement between repeated measurements can reflect the characteristics of the measurement instrument, reliability is influenced by both the magnitude of errors and true heterogeneity in the subjects being measured. This means that reliability estimates are limited in their generalizability to populations with similar heterogeneity. Consequently, reliability estimates should only be compared if they have been derived from the same population, where the underlying true values exhibit similar variation [9].

Intraclass Correlation Coefficient

The ICC is a dimensionless index used to assess the reliability of measurements within groups of subjects. It is calculated by partitioning the total variance into between-subject and within-subject variances, based on ANOVA [14]. The ICC was first introduced by Fisher in 1954 as an adaptation of the Pearson correlation coefficient [18]. He demonstrated that ICC could be estimated using the mean squares (MS) from the one-way ANOVA [10, 19]. In 1979, Shrout and Fleiss [20] expanded the concept of the ICC by introducing six different forms based on one-way and two-way ANOVA. They also provided guidelines for selecting the appropriate form based on specific study designs. Later, in 1996, McGraw and Wong [21] introduced additional forms of the ICC to assess both absolute agreement (ICC(A, 1) and ICC(A, k)) and consistency (ICC(C, 1) and ICC(C, k)) among measurements, along with further guidelines to assist researchers in choosing the most suitable method for their study.

The ICC is fundamentally rooted in the concept of the reliability coefficient, which is defined as the ratio of the variance of the true values to the variance of the observed measurements:

$$R = \frac{\sigma_{true}^2}{\sigma_{observed}^2} = \frac{\sigma_{true}^2}{\sigma_{true}^2 + \sigma_{error}^2}$$

Since the true value of each subject is unknown, the variance of true values (σ_{true}^2) is also unknown. However, as Fisher demonstrated [7, 10, 18], it can be estimated using the between-subjects variability – the variance attributable to differences between subjects. Consequently, the reliability coefficient can be reformulated as follows [15]:

$$R = \frac{\text{Between Subjects Variability}}{\text{Between Subject Variability} + \text{Error Variability}}$$

This basic formula serves as the foundation for the development of different ICCs. The various ICC formulas arise from distinct study designs, each with specific assumptions about the sources of variability in the data. These sources can include both random and/or fixed effects, and whether there is an interaction between these sources. For each study design, a corresponding ANOVA model is developed to account for the defined sources of variability.

Within the ANOVA framework, the sum of squares (SS) quantifies the variability attributable to each source, such as between-subject variability and error variability. These sums of squares are used to calculate MS, which represent the average variability for each source. The expected mean squares (EMS) are then expressed in terms of the variances associated with each source of variability. Finally, based on the underlying ANOVA model and the EMS values, the ICC formula specific to each study design can be derived [20, 21].

Having discussed the fundamental principles and derivation of the ICC, it is crucial to understand how to select the appropriate ICC model for a given study. McGraw and Wong [21] provided a flowchart in their paper to assist researchers in selecting the appropriate ICC for their studies. Additionally, Koo and Li [18] offer a guideline that addresses the appropriate selection of ICC, specifically for test-retest and intra-rater reliability studies. Like McGraw and Wong, they also provide a flowchart facilitate the appropriate selection of ICC. According to both resources, the selection of the appropriate ICC model can be guided by four key questions:

1. Is there the same set of raters (or measurement instruments) for all subjects?
2. Are the raters randomly selected from a broader population, or is a particular set of raters used in the study?
3. Is the reliability of a single rater being measured, or the mean value of several raters?
4. Is absolute agreement between measurements or consistency among them being sought?

The first question helps determine whether a one-way or two-way model of ICC is more appropriate. If **each subject** is rated by a **different set of raters**, a one-way model is used. However, if all subjects are rated by the same set of raters, a two-way model would be more suitable. The second question aids in clarifying whether a random effects model or a mixed effects model – a model for random and fixed effects – should be applied. If raters are randomly selected from a larger population, a random effects model is appropriate. On the other hand, if the raters are specifically chosen (e.g. three specific measurement instruments), a mixed effects model is recommended. The third question helps determine the appropriate ICC type. If the assessment is based on the mean value of multiple raters, the 'mean of k raters' type should be selected. Conversely, if the measurement from a single rater is used as the basis for the assessment, the 'single rater' type should be chosen, regardless of the number of raters involved in the study. Finally, the last question helps specify the ICC definition. If absolute agreement is prioritized, it focuses on whether different raters assign the exact same score to the same subject. In contrast, if consistency is the focus, it refers to the degree to which raters' scores for the same subjects are correlated, allowing for some systematic error, but maintaining a consistent ranking of subjects across raters [18].

Following the choice of the correct ICC model, it's important to understand both its value and interpretation. The ICC value ranges from 0 to 1, with values closer to 1 indicating higher reliability [14]. Its interpretation is relatively straightforward, as it represents the proportion of variance in the measurements attributable to the variance of the true values [15]. For instance, an ICC of 0.87 means that 87% of the observed variance in the measurements is due to true differences between subjects, while the remaining 13% is due to errors in the measurement process [9, 15]. However, determining whether this ICC represents an accepted level of reliability is not always straightforward. It is not theoretically defensible to set a universal threshold for ICC value reliability [22]. While some sources attempt to categorize ICC values as 'good,' 'medium,' or 'poor,' there is no universally agreed-upon standard for acceptable ICC values, and certainly no consensus on what constitutes an acceptable ICC value [15, 18]. The interpretation of the ICC is further complicated by two factors. First, the value of the ICC varies

depending on the specific version of the ICC used. Second, the magnitude of the ICC is influenced by the variability among the subjects being measured [15]. Thus, the interpretation of ICC should always be considered within the context of the study and its particular characteristics.

Relationship Between CCC and ICC

The CCC was originally introduced as a distinct index from the ICC. However, Carrasco and Jover [23] demonstrated that, when the observers are treated as a fixed effect and agreement among them is desired, the ICC, as defined by Shrout and Fleiss, becomes mathematically **identical** to the CCC. This equivalence arises when the variances of the model's variability effects are expressed through the means, variances, and covariances of the measurements to derive the respective ICC, resulting in a formulation that is similar to the CCC formula.

In the current study, the ICC(A, 1) defined by McGraw and Wong is used, which differs from the ICC model proposed by Shrout and Fleiss. Chen and Barnhart [11] pointed out that the ICC(A, 1) used in this study does not generally equal the CCC, and its value is influenced by factors such as the number of subjects, the number of observers (measurement instruments), and the number of replications in the data. They found that the ICC(A, 1) equals the CCC when there is only one replication in the data. However, this scenario is not typical in repeatability and reproducibility studies, where multiple replications are typically involved. As the number of replications increases, the ICC(A, 1) value rises quickly and surpasses the CCC value, which is expected in this study.

Inappropriate Statistical Metrics for Evaluating Agreement and Reliability

Certain statistical metrics, though widely used, are not suitable for assessing agreement and reliability between measurements. While these metrics may provide useful information about relationships or variations, they fail to adequately address the criteria needed to assess agreement or estimate reliability. This section explores why some commonly used statistical measures are inadequate for these purposes.

Paired T-Test and Repeated-Measures ANOVA Test

The paired t-test and repeated-measures ANOVA are both tests designed to assess the equality of means between two sets of paired measurements (X, Y):

- The paired t-test tests the null hypothesis that the mean difference between the two measurements is zero, i.e., $\mu_d = 0$.
- The repeated-measures ANOVA tests the null hypothesis that there are no differences in the means across the different measurements, i.e., $\mu_y = \mu_x$.

However, as tests of equality of means, both these methods have limited power when it comes to assessing **agreement** and **reliability**. According to the mathematical definition of agreement, it is possible for the measurements to have equal means (e.g., $\mu_d = 0$ in the paired t-test, or $\mu_y = \mu_x$ in the repeated-measures ANOVA), yet still not exhibit good agreement. This is because the two measurements may have considerably different variances, leading to unacceptably large variability in the differences around zero (i.e., large σ_d^2), even when the correlation between the measurements is high. This limitation also applies to **reliability**. While ANOVA can partition the total variance into different sources, these tests do not directly quantify the proportion of variance attributed to true measurement values versus measurement error, which is essential for a thorough reliability assessment [5, 14].

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient

Pearson's correlation coefficient provides valuable information about the association between two sets of measurements, but it does not necessarily reflect their reliability or the extent of agreement between them. Correlation is a measure of the linear relationship between variables, indicating whether they vary together, but it doesn't address whether the measurements are close or consistent in value. It also fails to capture systematic errors. As a result, two sets of measurements could be highly correlated, yet still exhibit poor agreement or low reliability [5, 14].

Coefficient of Determination of Linear Regression

The ordinary linear regression is used to estimate the linear relationship between an observed response (dependent variable) and factors (independent variables) that may influence the response [24]. In this context, one might consider Y as the response variable, and X as the explanatory variable. The linear regression assumes that the explanatory variable is error-free, while only the response variable is measured with error [5]. However, this assumption is not valid in studies where there is no ground truth or error-free measurement, as is the case here. The coefficient of determination, R^2 , represents the proportion of variability in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variable through the regression equation. An R^2 value of 1 indicates that the regression equation explains all the variability of the dependent variable, while a value of 0 indicates that the regression equation explains none of the variability [24]. As the definition of R^2 suggests, it is not suitable for measuring agreement or reliability because it does not address the differences between the means of two sets of measurements, nor does it assess the equality of variances – both of which are essential for evaluating agreement. Moreover, R^2 does not provide a way to estimate the proportion of variance that reflects reliability.

Coefficient of Variation

The Coefficient of Variation (CV) is a frequently used estimate of measurement error, particularly in laboratory studies where repeated testing is standard practice. It is typically calculated by dividing the standard deviation of the data by the mean and multiplying by 100 to express it as a percentage. This formulation expresses the standard deviation as a proportion of the mean, making it unit-independent. However, while CV can provide insight into the relative variability of the data, it is not suitable for measuring agreement or reliability. CV does not directly estimate the actual amount of measurement error, nor does it offer insight into the proportion of variance that indicates reliability. As a unit-less metric, CV does not offer insight into the equality of means or variances between measurements, making it inappropriate for assessing agreement [14].

Detailed Statistical Analysis Design

In the context of statistical analysis, each reconstruction, characterized by a distinct potential or energy level, is treated as a measurement from an individual rater. The algorithm that generates the reconstruction serves as a separate rater, evaluating the scan data by producing images. According to a review by Traverso et al. [25], different tube currents were shown to have no significant effect on feature reproducibility. Consequently, in this study, the analysis incorporates data from all scans, with each phantom providing values from all three tube currents. Specifically, for the 16 phantoms, this results in three values per phantom, leading to a total of 48 values for each analysis case. Based on this premise, the statistical analysis can be designed accordingly.

The statistical analysis can be broken down into three main parts:

1. Repeatability Analysis
2. Reproducibility Analysis
3. Agreement and Reliability Analysis of the Average Values of the Radiomic Features in Test and Retest Scans, Before and After the Rotation of Phantoms

The analysis will report the number of radiomic features that show agreement exceeding the predefined threshold of 0.9 for high agreement in each comparison case. The same approach will be applied to report the number of reliable radiomic features in each comparison case.

Before starting the data analysis, it is important to assess the normality of the radiomic feature values, as some metrics, as mentioned in the Theoretical Basis for Statistical Analysis, are sensitive to the normality of datasets. Therefore, the normality of the radiomic feature values is evaluated using the Shapiro-Wilk statistical test [26]. For the sake of simplicity, in this study, the repeatability and reproducibility were evaluated only for phantoms in the initial position.

Repeatability Analysis

In this section, repeatability is assessed by comparing the radiomic features of reconstructions with the same potential or energy level, in line with the definition of repeatability. The objective is to evaluate the agreement and reliability of the extracted features across test and retest scans. For PER, repeatability will be assessed in a single case, as only one PER is available. For VMER, repeatability will be evaluated across 16 different energy levels.

Reproducibility Analysis

In this section, reproducibility is assessed by comparing the radiomic features of reconstructions with different potential and energy levels, in accordance with the definition of reproducibility. Comparisons can be made within a single scan, referred to as *intra-scan reproducibility*, to assess the intrinsic reproducibility of the radiomic features. Alternatively, comparisons can be made between test and retest scans, referred to as *inter-scan reproducibility*. The objective is to evaluate the agreement and reliability of the extracted features for each type of comparison.

Intra-Scan Reproducibility

Intra-scan reproducibility focuses on the intrinsic reproducibility of the radiomic features in the **test scan**, where the phantoms are in their **initial state**. There are 16 comparison cases for assessing the reproducibility of both PER and VMER, as only one PER and 16 VMER with distinct energy levels are available. To assess the reproducibility across the different energy levels of the VMER, 120 comparison cases are to be evaluated.

Inter-Scan Reproducibility

Inter-scan reproducibility focuses on the reproducibility of the radiomic features between the **test** and **retest** scans. For assessing the reproducibility of the PER and VMER, there are 16 comparison cases, as there is only one PER and 16 VMER with distinct energy levels. For VMER, reproducibility will be evaluated across 120 comparison cases.

Agreement and Reliability Analysis of the Average Values of the Radiomic Features in Test and Retest Scans, Before and After the Rotation of Phantoms

This section focuses on studying the effect of phantom rotation on the values of the radiomic features. Since rotating the phantoms does not alter the subjects being measured or the measurement conditions, the impact of this change in orientation does not strictly fit within the predefined statistical definitions of repeatability and reproducibility. However, following the definition of repeatability, this analysis is more closely related to a repeatability study.

To assess the impact of phantom rotation, the average value of all radiomic features for reconstructions with the same potential or energy level is first calculated for both test and retest scans, in both the initial and rotated states. Then, the agreement and reliability of these averages are evaluated.

For PER, only one comparison case is considered, as there is a single PER available. For VMER, 16 comparison cases are included, corresponding to the 16 different energy levels.

Proper Metric Selection

It is important to highlight that the statistical analysis comprises 306 comparison cases, each involving the assessment of 91 radiomic features. As previously mentioned, shape features are excluded from this analysis because they are dependent on segmentation rather than texture. Given the large number of features and comparisons, applying absolute metrics of agreement and reliability would not be appropriate for this study.

The primary challenge with absolute metrics is that the thresholds for high agreement or reliability would be heavily dependent on the specific values, units, and ranges of each radiomic feature across various reconstructions and scans. This variability would require separate evaluations for each feature in every comparison and scan, which would go beyond the scope of the study and its intended focus.

Instead, relative metrics provide a more suitable approach for analysing large datasets like this one. Relative metrics focus on the proportional differences between the values, offering a consistent framework for evaluating agreement and reliability regardless of the specific units or ranges of the features. In this study, relative metrics are employed to assess the agreement and reliability of the radiomic features, ensuring a more efficient and consistent analysis across the entire dataset.

Metric for Assessment of Agreement

In this study, the CCC is used as a relative metric, which is generally robust against moderate deviations from normality [10], to evaluate the agreement between two sets of radiomic feature values.

Some references [27-29] have suggested specific thresholds for acceptable CCC values depending on the context of their studies. However, it is important to note that the interpretation of correlation coefficients varies across different scientific fields, and there is no

universal standard for assessing their strength [28]. This variability is particularly relevant for radiomic features, which can differ widely in terms of values, units, and ranges. Consequently, some other references [5, 10] simply state that large positive CCC values indicate good agreement without specifying a particular threshold for acceptable or good agreement.

In this study, a CCC value of 0.9 or greater is considered to demonstrate good agreement. This threshold is chosen because a CCC value above 0.9 typically indicates a high level of concordance between measurements, meaning that the observed variation between the datasets is minimal.

Selection of Proper Reliability Metric

In this study, the ICC is used as a relative metric, which is relatively robust to mild deviations from normality [30], to assess the reliability between two sets of radiomic feature values.

Several references have proposed a minimum acceptable threshold for ICC, while others define ranges to categorize ICC values as reflecting poor, acceptable, or good reliability [31-33]. The selection of the threshold for ICC follows the same rationale as for CCC, as discussed earlier. Given that there is no universal standard for interpreting correlation coefficients, the threshold in this study is determined based on the definition of reliability and ICC, and the guideline established by Koo and Li [18]. Accordingly, an ICC value of 0.9 or greater is considered to indicate good reliability, reflecting that 90% or more of the observed variance in the radiomic feature values is due to true differences between subjects, while the remaining 10% or less is due to errors in the measurement process.

Selection of Proper ICC Version

The selection of the appropriate ICC version is primarily determined by addressing the four questions outlined in the Intraclass Correlation Coefficient section, using either the ICC versions defined by Shrout and Fleiss [20] or by McGraw and Wong [21]. Additionally, the guideline provided by Koo and Li [18] offers straightforward assistance in selecting the correct version of ICC.

It is important to emphasize that the primary objective of this study is to evaluate the reliability of measurements made by a fixed set of raters (reconstructions) in terms of absolute agreement. As described in the Detailed Statistical Analysis Design section, all subjects in the comparison cases are rated by a specific rater from this fixed set. Therefore, it is clear that, in all three parts of the study, a version of ICC using a two-way mixed-effects model should be applied. For both the repeatability and reproducibility analyses, no averaged values are involved. However, in the Agreement and Reliability Analysis of the Average Values of the Radiomic Features in Test and Retest Scans, Before and After the Rotation of Phantoms section, the analysis is based on the average values of two conditions (initial and rotated).

Taking these details into account, the specific selected ICC model for each part of the study, according to McGraw and Wong [21], is as follows:

- Repeatability Analyses: ICC(A, 1)
- Reproducibility Analyses: ICC(A, 1)
- Analyses of Average Values of Radiomic Features in Test and Retest Scans, Before and After Rotation of Phantoms: ICC(A, 2)

Results

Normality Analysis Results

Test Scan, Initial State

On average, the normality of 71 radiomic features (nearly 79% of the features) is rejected across all reconstructions in the test scan, where the phantoms were in their initial position. Among the different reconstructions, the VMER with energy levels of 80 and 90 keV show the highest number of non-normal features, with 76 non-normal features (83.5%) each. In contrast, the VMER with an energy level of 40 keV shows the fewest non-normal features, with 64 (circa 70%). The PER falls between these extremes.

Average Non-normal Ratio: 78.2%

Average Number of Non-Normal Features: 71

Table S1 – Normality of radiomic feature values in test scan in initial state

Reconstruction	Characteristic	Scan	State	Non-Normal Features	Non-Normal Features Ratio	Normal Features	Normal Features Ratio
Polyenergetic	120 kV	Test	Initial	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22
Monoenergetic	40 keV	Test	Initial	64/91	0.70	27/91	0.30
Monoenergetic	50 keV	Test	Initial	68/91	0.75	23/91	0.25
Monoenergetic	60 keV	Test	Initial	69/91	0.76	22/91	0.24
Monoenergetic	70 keV	Test	Initial	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	80 keV	Test	Initial	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16
Monoenergetic	90 keV	Test	Initial	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16
Monoenergetic	100 keV	Test	Initial	74/91	0.81	17/91	0.19
Monoenergetic	110 keV	Test	Initial	73/91	0.80	18/91	0.20
Monoenergetic	120 keV	Test	Initial	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	130 keV	Test	Initial	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	140 keV	Test	Initial	70/91	0.77	21/91	0.23
Monoenergetic	150 keV	Test	Initial	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22
Monoenergetic	160 keV	Test	Initial	70/91	0.77	21/91	0.23
Monoenergetic	170 keV	Test	Initial	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22
Monoenergetic	180 keV	Test	Initial	70/91	0.77	21/91	0.23
Monoenergetic	190 keV	Test	Initial	70/91	0.77	21/91	0.23

Retest Scan, Initial State

Among all reconstructions in the retest scan, where the phantoms were in their initial state, an average of 71 radiomic features (about 79%) do not follow a normal distribution. The VMER with an energy level of 80 keV shows the highest number of non-normal features, with 78 (close to 86%). In contrast, the VMER with an energy level of 40 keV has the fewest non-normal features, with 63 (around 69%). The PER falls between these extremes.

Average Non-normal Ratio: 78.9%

Average Number of Non-Normal Features: 71

Table S2 – Normality of radiomic feature values in retest scan in initial state

Reconstruction	Characteristic	Scan	State	Non-Normal Features	Non-Normal Features Ratio	Normal Features	Normal Features Ratio
Polyenergetic	120 kV	Retest	Initial	67/91	0.74	24/91	0.26
Monoenergetic	40 keV	Retest	Initial	63/91	0.69	28/91	0.31
Monoenergetic	50 keV	Retest	Initial	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22
Monoenergetic	60 keV	Retest	Initial	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22
Monoenergetic	70 keV	Retest	Initial	75/91	0.82	16/91	0.18
Monoenergetic	80 keV	Retest	Initial	78/91	0.86	13/91	0.14
Monoenergetic	90 keV	Retest	Initial	77/91	0.85	14/91	0.15
Monoenergetic	100 keV	Retest	Initial	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16
Monoenergetic	110 keV	Retest	Initial	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	120 keV	Retest	Initial	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	130 keV	Retest	Initial	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	140 keV	Retest	Initial	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	150 keV	Retest	Initial	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22
Monoenergetic	160 keV	Retest	Initial	70/91	0.77	21/91	0.23
Monoenergetic	170 keV	Retest	Initial	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22
Monoenergetic	180 keV	Retest	Initial	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22
Monoenergetic	190 keV	Retest	Initial	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22

Test Scan, Rotated State

For the test scan in the rotated state, an average of 76 radiomic features (83.5%) across all reconstructions fail to follow a normal distribution. The VMER with energy levels ranging from 60 to 120 keV exhibit the highest number of non-normal features, with 79 (nearly 87%). In contrast, the PER and the VMER at 40 keV show the fewest non-normal features, with 69 (circa 76%).

Average Non-normal Ratio: 84.2%

Average Number of Non-Normal Features: 76

Table S3 – Normality of radiomic feature values in test scan in rotated state

Reconstruction	Characteristic	Scan	State	Non-Normal Features	Non-Normal Features Ratio	Normal Features	Normal Features Ratio
Polyenergetic	120 kV	Test	Rotated	69/91	0.76	22/91	0.24
Monoenergetic	40 keV	Test	Rotated	69/91	0.76	22/91	0.24
Monoenergetic	50 keV	Test	Rotated	74/91	0.81	17/91	0.19
Monoenergetic	60 keV	Test	Rotated	79/91	0.87	12/91	0.13
Monoenergetic	70 keV	Test	Rotated	79/91	0.87	12/91	0.13
Monoenergetic	80 keV	Test	Rotated	79/91	0.87	12/91	0.13
Monoenergetic	90 keV	Test	Rotated	79/91	0.87	12/91	0.13
Monoenergetic	100 keV	Test	Rotated	79/91	0.87	12/91	0.13
Monoenergetic	110 keV	Test	Rotated	79/91	0.87	12/91	0.13
Monoenergetic	120 keV	Test	Rotated	79/91	0.87	12/91	0.13
Monoenergetic	130 keV	Test	Rotated	78/91	0.86	13/91	0.14
Monoenergetic	140 keV	Test	Rotated	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16
Monoenergetic	150 keV	Test	Rotated	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16
Monoenergetic	160 keV	Test	Rotated	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16
Monoenergetic	170 keV	Test	Rotated	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16
Monoenergetic	180 keV	Test	Rotated	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16
Monoenergetic	190 keV	Test	Rotated	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16

Retest Scan, Rotated State

In the retest scan with rotated phantoms, an average of 73 radiomic features (81%) do not follow a normal distribution. The VMER with an energy level of 70 keV shows the highest number of non-normal features, with 80 (roughly 88%). Meanwhile, the VMER with an energy level of 40 keV shows the fewest non-normal features, with 58 (around 64% of features).

Average Non-normal Ratio: 80.3%

Average Number of Non-Normal Features: 73

Table S4 – Normality of radiomic feature values in retest scan in rotated state

Reconstruction	Characteristic	Scan	State	Non-Normal Features	Non-Normal Features Ratio	Normal Features	Normal Features Ratio
Polyenergetic	120 kV	Retest	Rotated	80/91	0.88	11/91	0.12
Monoenergetic	40 keV	Retest	Rotated	58/91	0.64	33/91	0.36
Monoenergetic	50 keV	Retest	Rotated	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	60 keV	Retest	Rotated	76/91	0.84	15/91	0.16
Monoenergetic	70 keV	Retest	Rotated	80/91	0.88	11/91	0.12
Monoenergetic	80 keV	Retest	Rotated	77/91	0.85	14/91	0.15
Monoenergetic	90 keV	Retest	Rotated	75/91	0.82	16/91	0.18
Monoenergetic	100 keV	Retest	Rotated	74/91	0.81	17/91	0.19
Monoenergetic	110 keV	Retest	Rotated	73/91	0.80	18/91	0.20
Monoenergetic	120 keV	Retest	Rotated	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	130 keV	Retest	Rotated	73/91	0.80	18/91	0.20
Monoenergetic	140 keV	Retest	Rotated	73/91	0.80	18/91	0.20
Monoenergetic	150 keV	Retest	Rotated	73/91	0.80	18/91	0.20
Monoenergetic	160 keV	Retest	Rotated	72/91	0.79	19/91	0.21
Monoenergetic	170 keV	Retest	Rotated	73/91	0.80	18/91	0.20
Monoenergetic	180 keV	Retest	Rotated	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22
Monoenergetic	190 keV	Retest	Rotated	71/91	0.78	20/91	0.22

Repeatability Analysis

Polyenergetic Reconstruction

Repeatable Features in Test and Retest Scans in Initial State

Average High CCC Ratio: 65.9%

Average High ICC Ratio: 67.0%

Average Number of High CCC Features: 60

Average Number of High ICC Features: 61

Table S5 – Repeatability of polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans in initial state

Study	Comparison Case	High_CCC	High_CCC_No	High_ICC	High_ICC_No
Repeatability	120 kV	65.93%	60/91	67.03%	61/91

Feature Classes with High Agreement

Table S6 – Feature classes with high agreement in repeatability analysis of polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans in initial state

Comparison Case	FO	GLCM	GLSZM	GLRLM	NGTDM	GLDM
120 kV	13/18 (72.2%)	14/22 (63.6%)	9/16 (56.2%)	11/16 (68.8%)	3/5 (60.0%)	10/14 (71.4%)

Feature Classes with High Reliability

Table S7 – Feature classes with high reliability in repeatability analysis of polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans in initial state

Comparison Case	FO	GLCM	GLSZM	GLRLM	NGTDM	GLDM
120 kV	13/18 (72.2%)	15/22 (68.2%)	9/16 (56.2%)	11/16 (68.8%)	3/5 (60.0%)	10/14 (71.4%)

Names of Features with High Agreement

Table S8 – Feature names with high agreement in repeatability analysis of polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Entropy
5	FO	InterquartileRange
6	FO	Maximum
7	FO	Mean
8	FO	Median
9	FO	RobustMeanAbsoluteDeviation
10	FO	RootMeanSquared
11	FO	Skewness
12	FO	TotalEnergy
13	FO	Uniformity
14	GLCM	ClusterProminence
15	GLCM	Correlation
16	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
17	GLCM	DifferenceEntropy

18	GLCM	Id
19	GLCM	Idm
20	GLCM	Idn
21	GLCM	Imc1
22	GLCM	Imc2
23	GLCM	InverseVariance
24	GLCM	JointEnergy
25	GLCM	JointEntropy
26	GLCM	MaximumProbability
27	GLCM	SumEntropy
28	GLDM	DependenceEntropy
29	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformity
30	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformityNormalized
31	GLDM	DependenceVariance
32	GLDM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
33	GLDM	LargeDependenceEmphasis
34	GLDM	LargeDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
35	GLDM	LargeDependenceLowGrayLevelEmphasis
36	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
37	GLDM	SmallDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
38	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
39	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
40	GLRLM	LongRunEmphasis
41	GLRLM	LongRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
42	GLRLM	LongRunLowGrayLevelEmphasis
43	GLRLM	RunEntropy
44	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
45	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformityNormalized
46	GLRLM	RunPercentage
47	GLRLM	RunVariance
48	GLRLM	ShortRunEmphasis
49	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
50	GLSZM	LargeAreaEmphasis
51	GLSZM	LargeAreaHighGrayLevelEmphasis
52	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
53	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
54	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
55	GLSZM	ZoneEntropy
56	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
57	GLSZM	ZoneVariance
58	NGTDM	Busyness
59	NGTDM	Coarseness
60	NGTDM	Strength

Names of Features with High Reliability

Table S9 – Feature names with high reliability in repeatability analysis of polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Entropy
5	FO	InterquartileRange
6	FO	Maximum
7	FO	Mean
8	FO	Median
9	FO	RobustMeanAbsoluteDeviation

10	FO	RootMeanSquared
11	FO	Skewness
12	FO	TotalEnergy
13	FO	Uniformity
14	GLCM	ClusterProminence
15	GLCM	Correlation
16	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
17	GLCM	DifferenceEntropy
18	GLCM	Id
19	GLCM	Idm
20	GLCM	Idmn
21	GLCM	Idn
22	GLCM	Imc1
23	GLCM	Imc2
24	GLCM	InverseVariance
25	GLCM	JointEnergy
26	GLCM	JointEntropy
27	GLCM	MaximumProbability
28	GLCM	SumEntropy
29	GLDM	DependenceEntropy
30	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformity
31	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformityNormalized
32	GLDM	DependenceVariance
33	GLDM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
34	GLDM	LargeDependenceEmphasis
35	GLDM	LargeDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
36	GLDM	LargeDependenceLowGrayLevelEmphasis
37	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
38	GLDM	SmallDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
39	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
40	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
41	GLRLM	LongRunEmphasis
42	GLRLM	LongRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
43	GLRLM	LongRunLowGrayLevelEmphasis
44	GLRLM	RunEntropy
45	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
46	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformityNormalized
47	GLRLM	RunPercentage
48	GLRLM	RunVariance
49	GLRLM	ShortRunEmphasis
50	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
51	GLSZM	LargeAreaEmphasis
52	GLSZM	LargeAreaHighGrayLevelEmphasis
53	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
54	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
55	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
56	GLSZM	ZoneEntropy
57	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
58	GLSZM	ZoneVariance
59	NGTDM	Busyness
60	NGTDM	Coarseness
61	NGTDM	Strength

Virtual Monoenergetic Reconstruction

Repeatable Features in Test and Retest Scans in Initial State

Average High CCC Ratio: 94.1%

Average High ICC Ratio: 94.2%

Average Number of High CCC Features: 85

Average Number of High ICC Features: 85

Table S10 – Repeatability of virtual monoenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans in initial state

Study	Comparison Case	High_CCC	High_CCC_No	High_ICC	High_ICC_No
Repeatability	40 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Repeatability	50 keV	92.31%	84/91	92.31%	84/91
Repeatability	60 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Repeatability	70 keV	94.51%	86/91	94.51%	86/91
Repeatability	80 keV	93.41%	85/91	94.51%	86/91
Repeatability	90 keV	94.51%	86/91	94.51%	86/91
Repeatability	100 keV	94.51%	86/91	94.51%	86/91
Repeatability	110 keV	95.60%	87/91	95.60%	87/91
Repeatability	120 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Repeatability	130 keV	92.31%	84/91	92.31%	84/91
Repeatability	140 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Repeatability	150 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Repeatability	160 keV	93.41%	85/91	94.51%	86/91
Repeatability	170 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Repeatability	180 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Repeatability	190 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91

Figure S1 – Repeatability of the virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans

Feature Classes with High Agreement

Repeatability of VMERs in Test and Retest Scans Before Rotation of Phantoms

Figure S2 – Feature classes with high agreement in repeatability analysis of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

Feature Classes with High Reliability

Repeatability of VMERs in Test and Retest Scans Before Rotation of Phantoms

Figure S3 – Feature classes with high reliability in repeatability analysis of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

Names of Features with High Agreement in All Cases

Table S11 – Feature names with high agreement in repeatability analysis of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Entropy
5	FO	InterquartileRange
6	FO	Kurtosis
7	FO	Maximum
8	FO	Mean
9	FO	MeanAbsoluteDeviation
10	FO	Median
11	FO	Minimum
12	FO	Range
13	FO	RobustMeanAbsoluteDeviation
14	FO	RootMeanSquared
15	FO	Skewness
16	FO	TotalEnergy
17	FO	Uniformity
18	FO	Variance
19	GLCM	Autocorrelation
20	GLCM	ClusterProminence
21	GLCM	ClusterShade
22	GLCM	ClusterTendency
23	GLCM	Contrast
24	GLCM	Correlation
25	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
26	GLCM	DifferenceEntropy
27	GLCM	DifferenceVariance
28	GLCM	Id
29	GLCM	Idm
30	GLCM	Idmn
31	GLCM	Idn
32	GLCM	Imc1
33	GLCM	Imc2
34	GLCM	InverseVariance
35	GLCM	JointAverage
36	GLCM	JointEnergy
37	GLCM	JointEntropy
38	GLCM	MaximumProbability
39	GLCM	SumEntropy
40	GLCM	SumSquares
41	GLDM	DependenceEntropy
42	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformity
43	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformityNormalized
44	GLDM	DependenceVariance
45	GLDM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
46	GLDM	GrayLevelVariance
47	GLDM	HighGrayLevelEmphasis
48	GLDM	LargeDependenceEmphasis
49	GLDM	LargeDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
50	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
51	GLDM	SmallDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
52	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
53	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
54	GLRLM	GrayLevelVariance

55	GLRLM	HighGrayLevelRunEmphasis
56	GLRLM	LongRunEmphasis
57	GLRLM	LongRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
58	GLRLM	LongRunLowGrayLevelEmphasis
59	GLRLM	RunEntropy
60	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
61	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformityNormalized
62	GLRLM	RunPercentage
63	GLRLM	RunVariance
64	GLRLM	ShortRunEmphasis
65	GLRLM	ShortRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
66	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
67	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
68	GLSZM	GrayLevelVariance
69	GLSZM	HighGrayLevelZoneEmphasis
70	GLSZM	LargeAreaEmphasis
71	GLSZM	LargeAreaHighGrayLevelEmphasis
72	GLSZM	LargeAreaLowGrayLevelEmphasis
73	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
74	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
75	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
76	GLSZM	ZoneEntropy
77	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
78	GLSZM	ZoneVariance
79	NGTDM	Busyness
80	NGTDM	Coarseness
81	NGTDM	Complexity
82	NGTDM	Contrast
83	NGTDM	Strength

Names of Features with High Reliability in All Cases

Table S12 – Feature names with high reliability in repeatability analysis of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Entropy
5	FO	InterquartileRange
6	FO	Kurtosis
7	FO	Maximum
8	FO	Mean
9	FO	MeanAbsoluteDeviation
10	FO	Median
11	FO	Minimum
12	FO	Range
13	FO	RobustMeanAbsoluteDeviation
14	FO	RootMeanSquared
15	FO	Skewness
16	FO	TotalEnergy
17	FO	Uniformity
18	FO	Variance
19	GLCM	Autocorrelation
20	GLCM	ClusterProminence
21	GLCM	ClusterShade
22	GLCM	ClusterTendency
23	GLCM	Contrast
24	GLCM	Correlation
25	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
26	GLCM	DifferenceEntropy
27	GLCM	DifferenceVariance
28	GLCM	Id
29	GLCM	Idm
30	GLCM	Idmn
31	GLCM	Idn
32	GLCM	Imc1
33	GLCM	Imc2
34	GLCM	InverseVariance
35	GLCM	JointAverage
36	GLCM	JointEnergy
37	GLCM	JointEntropy
38	GLCM	MaximumProbability
39	GLCM	SumEntropy
40	GLCM	SumSquares
41	GLDM	DependenceEntropy
42	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformity
43	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformityNormalized
44	GLDM	DependenceVariance
45	GLDM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
46	GLDM	GrayLevelVariance
47	GLDM	HighGrayLevelEmphasis
48	GLDM	LargeDependenceEmphasis
49	GLDM	LargeDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
50	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
51	GLDM	SmallDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
52	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
53	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
54	GLRLM	GrayLevelVariance

55	GLRLM	HighGrayLevelRunEmphasis
56	GLRLM	LongRunEmphasis
57	GLRLM	LongRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
58	GLRLM	LongRunLowGrayLevelEmphasis
59	GLRLM	RunEntropy
60	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
61	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformityNormalized
62	GLRLM	RunPercentage
63	GLRLM	RunVariance
64	GLRLM	ShortRunEmphasis
65	GLRLM	ShortRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
66	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
67	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
68	GLSZM	GrayLevelVariance
69	GLSZM	HighGrayLevelZoneEmphasis
70	GLSZM	LargeAreaEmphasis
71	GLSZM	LargeAreaHighGrayLevelEmphasis
72	GLSZM	LargeAreaLowGrayLevelEmphasis
73	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
74	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
75	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
76	GLSZM	ZoneEntropy
77	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
78	GLSZM	ZoneVariance
79	NGTDM	Busyness
80	NGTDM	Coarseness
81	NGTDM	Complexity
82	NGTDM	Contrast
83	NGTDM	Strength

Reproducibility

Intra-Scan Reproducibility

Polyenergetic Reconstruction

Reproducible Features in Test Scan in Initial State

Average High CCC Ratio: 30.4%

Average High ICC Ratio: 31.2%

Average Number of High CCC Features: 27

Average Number of High ICC Features: 28

Table S13 – Intra-scan reproducibility of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

Study	Comparison Case	High_CCC	High_CCC_No	High_ICC	High_ICC_No
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 40 keV	24.18%	22/91	25.27%	23/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 50 keV	29.67%	27/91	29.67%	27/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 60 keV	43.96%	40/91	45.05%	41/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 70 keV	34.07%	31/91	38.46%	35/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 80 keV	31.87%	29/91	32.97%	30/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 90 keV	30.77%	28/91	30.77%	28/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 100 keV	30.77%	28/91	30.77%	28/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 110 keV	30.77%	28/91	30.77%	28/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 120 keV	30.77%	28/91	30.77%	28/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 130 keV	30.77%	28/91	30.77%	28/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 140 keV	29.67%	27/91	30.77%	28/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 150 keV	29.67%	27/91	29.67%	27/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 160 keV	27.47%	25/91	29.67%	27/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 170 keV	27.47%	25/91	28.57%	26/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 180 keV	27.47%	25/91	27.47%	25/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 190 keV	27.47%	25/91	27.47%	25/91

Figure S4 – Intra-scan reproducibility of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

Feature Classes with High Agreement

Reproducibility of PER and Different Energy Levels of VMERs in Test Scan Before Rotation of Phantoms

Figure S5 – Feature classes with high agreement in intra-scan reproducibility analysis of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

Feature Classes with High Reliability

Reproducibility of PER and Different Energy Levels of VMERs in Test Scan Before Rotation of Phantoms

Figure S6 – Feature classes with high reliability in intra-scan reproducibility analysis of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

Names of Features with High Agreement in All Cases

Table S14 – Feature names with high agreement in intra-scan reproducibility analysis of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	Median
6	FO	RootMeanSquared
7	FO	TotalEnergy
8	GLCM	ClusterTendency
9	GLCM	Idmn
10	GLCM	Idn
11	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
12	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
13	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
14	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
15	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
16	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
17	NGTDM	Busyness

Names of Features with High Reliability in All Cases

Table S15 – Feature names with high reliability in intra-scan reproducibility analysis of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	Median
6	FO	RootMeanSquared
7	FO	TotalEnergy
8	GLCM	ClusterTendency
9	GLCM	Idmn
10	GLCM	Idn
11	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
12	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
13	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
14	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
15	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
16	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
17	NGTDM	Busyness

Virtual Monoenergetic Reconstructions

Reproducible Features in Test Scan in Initial State

Average High CCC Ratio: 78.2%

Average High ICC Ratio: 78.5%

Average Number of High CCC Features: 71

Average Number of High ICC Features: 71

Table S16 – Intra-scan reproducibility of different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

Study	Comparison Case	High_CCC	High_CCC_No	High_ICC	High_ICC_No
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 50 keV	75.82%	69/91	75.82%	69/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 60 keV	51.65%	47/91	52.75%	48/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 70 keV	38.46%	35/91	38.46%	35/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 80 keV	36.26%	33/91	36.26%	33/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 90 keV	35.16%	32/91	35.16%	32/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 100 keV	31.87%	29/91	32.97%	30/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 110 keV	30.77%	28/91	30.77%	28/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 120 keV	28.57%	26/91	29.67%	27/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 130 keV	27.47%	25/91	27.47%	25/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 140 keV	27.47%	25/91	27.47%	25/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 150 keV	27.47%	25/91	27.47%	25/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 160 keV	27.47%	25/91	27.47%	25/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 170 keV	26.37%	24/91	27.47%	25/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 180 keV	25.27%	23/91	27.47%	25/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 190 keV	25.27%	23/91	26.37%	24/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 60 keV	78.02%	71/91	78.02%	71/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 70 keV	60.44%	55/91	60.44%	55/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 80 keV	53.85%	49/91	53.85%	49/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 90 keV	49.45%	45/91	49.45%	45/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 100 keV	48.35%	44/91	48.35%	44/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 110 keV	48.35%	44/91	48.35%	44/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 120 keV	47.25%	43/91	47.25%	43/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 130 keV	45.05%	41/91	45.05%	41/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 140 keV	43.96%	40/91	45.05%	41/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 150 keV	42.86%	39/91	42.86%	39/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 160 keV	42.86%	39/91	42.86%	39/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 170 keV	42.86%	39/91	42.86%	39/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 180 keV	41.76%	38/91	42.86%	39/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 190 keV	41.76%	38/91	42.86%	39/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 70 keV	87.91%	80/91	87.91%	80/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 80 keV	80.22%	73/91	80.22%	73/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 90 keV	74.73%	68/91	74.73%	68/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 100 keV	72.53%	66/91	72.53%	66/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 110 keV	64.84%	59/91	65.93%	60/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 120 keV	64.84%	59/91	64.84%	59/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 130 keV	64.84%	59/91	64.84%	59/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 140 keV	63.74%	58/91	63.74%	58/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 150 keV	63.74%	58/91	63.74%	58/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 160 keV	63.74%	58/91	63.74%	58/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 170 keV	63.74%	58/91	63.74%	58/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 180 keV	63.74%	58/91	63.74%	58/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 190 keV	63.74%	58/91	63.74%	58/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 80 keV	98.90%	90/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 90 keV	92.31%	84/91	92.31%	84/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 100 keV	85.71%	78/91	85.71%	78/91

Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 110 keV	81.32%	74/91	81.32%	74/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 120 keV	79.12%	72/91	79.12%	72/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 130 keV	74.73%	68/91	74.73%	68/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 140 keV	72.53%	66/91	73.63%	67/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 150 keV	72.53%	66/91	72.53%	66/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 160 keV	71.43%	65/91	71.43%	65/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 170 keV	70.33%	64/91	71.43%	65/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 180 keV	70.33%	64/91	70.33%	64/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 190 keV	69.23%	63/91	70.33%	64/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 90 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 100 keV	95.60%	87/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 110 keV	94.51%	86/91	95.60%	87/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 120 keV	94.51%	86/91	95.60%	87/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 130 keV	89.01%	81/91	90.11%	82/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 140 keV	83.52%	76/91	85.71%	78/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 150 keV	83.52%	76/91	83.52%	76/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 160 keV	81.32%	74/91	81.32%	74/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 170 keV	79.12%	72/91	80.22%	73/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 180 keV	79.12%	72/91	79.12%	72/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	80 keV vs. 190 keV	79.12%	72/91	79.12%	72/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 100 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 110 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 120 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 130 keV	98.90%	90/91	98.90%	90/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 140 keV	95.60%	87/91	95.60%	87/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 150 keV	95.60%	87/91	95.60%	87/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 160 keV	95.60%	87/91	95.60%	87/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 170 keV	95.60%	87/91	95.60%	87/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 180 keV	94.51%	86/91	94.51%	86/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	90 keV vs. 190 keV	92.31%	84/91	92.31%	84/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	100 keV vs. 110 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	100 keV vs. 120 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	100 keV vs. 130 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	100 keV vs. 140 keV	96.70%	88/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	100 keV vs. 150 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	100 keV vs. 160 keV	95.60%	87/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	100 keV vs. 170 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	100 keV vs. 180 keV	95.60%	87/91	95.60%	87/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	100 keV vs. 190 keV	95.60%	87/91	95.60%	87/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	110 keV vs. 120 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	110 keV vs. 130 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	110 keV vs. 140 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	110 keV vs. 150 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	110 keV vs. 160 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	110 keV vs. 170 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	110 keV vs. 180 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	110 keV vs. 190 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 keV vs. 130 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 keV vs. 140 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 keV vs. 150 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 keV vs. 160 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 keV vs. 170 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 keV vs. 180 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	120 keV vs. 190 keV	96.70%	88/91	96.70%	88/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	130 keV vs. 140 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	130 keV vs. 150 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	130 keV vs. 160 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	130 keV vs. 170 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	130 keV vs. 180 keV	97.80%	89/91	97.80%	89/91

Intra-Scan Reproducibility	130 keV vs. 190 keV	96.70%	88/91	97.80%	89/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 150 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 160 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 170 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 180 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 190 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	150 keV vs. 160 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	150 keV vs. 170 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	150 keV vs. 180 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	150 keV vs. 190 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	160 keV vs. 170 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	160 keV vs. 180 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	160 keV vs. 190 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	170 keV vs. 180 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	170 keV vs. 190 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91
Intra-Scan Reproducibility	180 keV vs. 190 keV	100.00%	91/91	100.00%	91/91

Figure S7 – Rounded percentage of reproducible features for each comparison case in intra-scan reproducibility analysis of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions

Reproducibility of Different Energy Levels of VMERs in Test Scan Before Rotation of Phantoms

Figure S8 – Intra-scan reproducibility of different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

Names of Features with High Agreement in All Cases

Table S17 – Feature names with high agreement in intra-scan reproducibility analysis of different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	Median
6	FO	RootMeanSquared
7	FO	TotalEnergy
8	GLCM	ClusterTendency
9	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
10	GLCM	Idn
11	GLCM	Imc1
12	GLCM	Imc2
13	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
14	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
15	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
16	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
17	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
18	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity

Names of Features with High Reliability in All Cases

Table S18 – Feature names with high reliability in intra-scan reproducibility analysis of different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test scan in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	Median
6	FO	RootMeanSquared
7	FO	Skewness
8	FO	TotalEnergy
9	GLCM	ClusterTendency
10	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
11	GLCM	Idn
12	GLCM	Imc1
13	GLCM	Imc2
14	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
15	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
16	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
17	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
18	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
19	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
20	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
21	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
22	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
23	NGTDM	Busyness
24	NGTDM	Strength

Inter-Scan Reproducibility

Polyenergetic Reconstruction

Reproducible Features in Test and Retest Scans in Initial State

Average High CCC Ratio: 30.4%

Average High ICC Ratio: 31.5%

Average Number of High CCC Features: 27

Average Number of High ICC Features: 28

Table S19 – Inter-scan reproducibility of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

Study	Comparison Case	High_CCC	High_CCC_No	High_ICC	High_ICC_No
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 40 keV	23.08%	21/91	24.18%	22/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 50 keV	30.77%	28/91	31.87%	29/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 60 keV	43.96%	40/91	46.15%	42/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 70 keV	36.26%	33/91	38.46%	35/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 80 keV	31.87%	29/91	32.97%	30/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 90 keV	30.77%	28/91	30.77%	28/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 100 keV	30.77%	28/91	30.77%	28/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 110 keV	29.67%	27/91	30.77%	28/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 120 keV	29.67%	27/91	29.67%	27/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 130 keV	29.67%	27/91	29.67%	27/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 140 keV	29.67%	27/91	29.67%	27/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 150 keV	28.57%	26/91	30.77%	28/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 160 keV	28.57%	26/91	30.77%	28/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 170 keV	28.57%	26/91	30.77%	28/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 180 keV	27.47%	25/91	28.57%	26/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	120 kV vs. 190 keV	27.47%	25/91	28.57%	26/91

Figure S11 – Inter-scan reproducibility of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

Feature Classes with High Agreement

Reproducibility of PER and VMERs in Test and Retest Scans Before Rotation of Phantoms

Figure S12 – Feature classes with high agreement in inter-scan reproducibility analysis of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

Feature Classes with High Reliability

Reproducibility of PER and VMERs in Test and Retest Scans Before Rotation of Phantoms

Figure S13 – Feature classes with high reliability in inter-scan reproducibility analysis of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

Names of Features with High Agreement in All Cases

Table S20 – Feature names with high agreement in inter-scan reproducibility analysis of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	Median
6	FO	RootMeanSquared
7	FO	TotalEnergy
8	GLCM	ClusterTendency
9	GLCM	Idn
10	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
11	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
12	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
13	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
14	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
15	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
16	NGTDM	Busyness

Names of Features with High Reliability in All Cases

Table S21 – Feature names with high reliability in inter-scan reproducibility analysis of polyenergetic and different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	Median
6	FO	RootMeanSquared
7	FO	TotalEnergy
8	GLCM	ClusterTendency
9	GLCM	Idn
10	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
11	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
12	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
13	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
14	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
15	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
16	NGTDM	Busyness

Virtual Monoenergetic Reconstructions

Reproducible Features in Test and Retest Scans in Initial State

Average High CCC Ratio: 74.1%

Average High ICC Ratio: 74.3%

Average Number of High CCC Features: 67

Average Number of High ICC Features: 67

Table S22 – Inter-scan reproducibility of different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

Study	Comparison Case	High_CCC	High_CCC_No	High_ICC	High_ICC_No
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 50 keV	68.13%	62/91	69.23%	63/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 60 keV	49.45%	45/91	49.45%	45/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 70 keV	38.46%	35/91	38.46%	35/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 80 keV	35.16%	32/91	35.16%	32/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 90 keV	32.97%	30/91	32.97%	30/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 100 keV	30.77%	28/91	30.77%	28/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 110 keV	27.47%	25/91	29.67%	27/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 120 keV	27.47%	25/91	27.47%	25/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 130 keV	27.47%	25/91	27.47%	25/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 140 keV	26.37%	24/91	27.47%	25/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 150 keV	26.37%	24/91	26.37%	24/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 160 keV	26.37%	24/91	26.37%	24/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 170 keV	26.37%	24/91	26.37%	24/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 180 keV	25.27%	23/91	25.27%	23/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	40 keV vs. 190 keV	25.27%	23/91	25.27%	23/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 60 keV	75.82%	69/91	76.92%	70/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 70 keV	56.04%	51/91	56.04%	51/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 80 keV	51.65%	47/91	51.65%	47/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 90 keV	49.45%	45/91	49.45%	45/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 100 keV	45.05%	41/91	46.15%	42/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 110 keV	43.96%	40/91	45.05%	41/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 120 keV	45.05%	41/91	45.05%	41/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 130 keV	45.05%	41/91	45.05%	41/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 140 keV	45.05%	41/91	45.05%	41/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 150 keV	43.96%	40/91	45.05%	41/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 160 keV	43.96%	40/91	43.96%	40/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 170 keV	43.96%	40/91	43.96%	40/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 180 keV	43.96%	40/91	43.96%	40/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	50 keV vs. 190 keV	43.96%	40/91	43.96%	40/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 70 keV	87.91%	80/91	87.91%	80/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 80 keV	81.32%	74/91	81.32%	74/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 90 keV	68.13%	62/91	68.13%	62/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 100 keV	65.93%	60/91	65.93%	60/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 110 keV	64.84%	59/91	64.84%	59/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 120 keV	62.64%	57/91	64.84%	59/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 130 keV	60.44%	55/91	62.64%	57/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 140 keV	60.44%	55/91	60.44%	55/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 150 keV	60.44%	55/91	60.44%	55/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 160 keV	60.44%	55/91	60.44%	55/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 170 keV	60.44%	55/91	60.44%	55/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 180 keV	60.44%	55/91	60.44%	55/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	60 keV vs. 190 keV	60.44%	55/91	60.44%	55/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 80 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 90 keV	89.01%	81/91	89.01%	81/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	70 keV vs. 100 keV	81.32%	74/91	81.32%	74/91

Inter-Scan Reproducibility	130 keV vs. 190 keV	92.31%	84/91	92.31%	84/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 150 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 160 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 170 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 180 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	140 keV vs. 190 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	150 keV vs. 160 keV	94.51%	86/91	94.51%	86/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	150 keV vs. 170 keV	93.41%	85/91	94.51%	86/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	150 keV vs. 180 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	150 keV vs. 190 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	160 keV vs. 170 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	160 keV vs. 180 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	160 keV vs. 190 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	170 keV vs. 180 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	170 keV vs. 190 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91
Inter-Scan Reproducibility	180 keV vs. 190 keV	93.41%	85/91	93.41%	85/91

Figure S14 – Rounded percentage of reproducible features for each comparison case in inter-scan reproducibility analysis of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions

Reproducibility of Different Energy Levels of VMERS in Test and Retest Scans Before Rotation of Phantoms

Figure S15 – Inter-scan reproducibility of different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

Names of Features with High Agreement in All Cases

Table S23 – Feature names with high agreement in inter-scan reproducibility analysis of different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	Median
6	FO	RootMeanSquared
7	FO	TotalEnergy
8	GLCM	ClusterTendency
9	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
10	GLCM	Idn
11	GLCM	Imc1
12	GLCM	Imc2
13	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
14	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
15	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
16	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
17	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
18	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
19	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
20	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
21	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
22	NGTDM	Busyness
23	NGTDM	Strength

Names of Features with High Reliability in All Cases

Table S24 – Feature names with high reliability in inter-scan reproducibility analysis of different energy levels of virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans in initial state

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	Median
6	FO	RootMeanSquared
7	FO	TotalEnergy
8	GLCM	ClusterTendency
9	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
10	GLCM	Idn
11	GLCM	Imc1
12	GLCM	Imc2
13	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
14	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
15	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
16	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
17	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
18	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
19	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
20	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
21	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
22	NGTDM	Busyness
23	NGTDM	Strength

Agreement and Reliability of Averages Values Before and After Rotation of Phantoms

Polyenergetic reconstruction

Features with High Agreement and Reliability

Average High CCC Ratio: 64.8%

Average High ICC Ratio: 72.5%

Average Number of High CCC Features: 59

Average Number of High ICC Features: 66

Table S25 – Analysis results of average values of radiomic features extracted from polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

Study	Comparison Case	High_CCC	High_CCC_No	High_ICC	High_ICC_No
Agreement and Reliability	120 kV	64.84%	59/91	72.53%	66/91

Feature Classes with High Agreement

Table S26 – Feature classes with high agreement in analysis of average values of radiomic features extracted from polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

Comparison Case	FO	GLCM	GLSZM	GLRLM	NGTDM	GLDM
120 kV	13/18 (72.2%)	14/22 (63.6%)	9/16 (56.2%)	11/16 (68.8%)	3/5 (60.0%)	9/14 (64.3%)

Feature Classes with High Reliability

Table S27 – Feature classes with high reliability in analysis of average values of radiomic features extracted from polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

Comparison Case	FO	GLCM	GLSZM	GLRLM	NGTDM	GLDM
120 kV	15/18 (83.3%)	17/22 (77.3%)	9/16 (56.2%)	11/16 (68.8%)	4/5 (80.0%)	10/14 (71.4%)

Names of Features with High Agreement

Table S28 – Feature names with high agreement in analysis of average values of radiomic features extracted from polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Entropy
5	FO	InterquartileRange
6	FO	Kurtosis
7	FO	Mean
8	FO	Median
9	FO	RobustMeanAbsoluteDeviation
10	FO	RootMeanSquared
11	FO	Skewness
12	FO	TotalEnergy
13	FO	Uniformity
14	GLCM	ClusterProminence
15	GLCM	Correlation
16	GLCM	DifferenceAverage

17	GLCM	DifferenceEntropy
18	GLCM	Id
19	GLCM	Idm
20	GLCM	Idn
21	GLCM	Imc1
22	GLCM	Imc2
23	GLCM	InverseVariance
24	GLCM	JointEnergy
25	GLCM	JointEntropy
26	GLCM	MaximumProbability
27	GLCM	SumEntropy
28	GLDM	DependenceEntropy
29	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformity
30	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformityNormalized
31	GLDM	DependenceVariance
32	GLDM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
33	GLDM	LargeDependenceEmphasis
34	GLDM	LargeDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
35	GLDM	LargeDependenceLowGrayLevelEmphasis
36	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
37	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
38	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
39	GLRLM	LongRunEmphasis
40	GLRLM	LongRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
41	GLRLM	LongRunLowGrayLevelEmphasis
42	GLRLM	RunEntropy
43	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
44	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformityNormalized
45	GLRLM	RunPercentage
46	GLRLM	RunVariance
47	GLRLM	ShortRunEmphasis
48	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
49	GLSZM	LargeAreaEmphasis
50	GLSZM	LargeAreaHighGrayLevelEmphasis
51	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
52	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
53	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
54	GLSZM	ZoneEntropy
55	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
56	GLSZM	ZoneVariance
57	NGTDM	Busyness
58	NGTDM	Coarseness
59	NGTDM	Strength

Names of Features with High Reliability

Table S29 – Feature names with high reliability in analysis of average values of radiomic features extracted from polyenergetic reconstruction in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	10Percentile
2	FO	90Percentile
3	FO	Energy
4	FO	Entropy
5	FO	InterquartileRange
6	FO	Kurtosis
7	FO	Maximum
8	FO	Mean
9	FO	MeanAbsoluteDeviation

10	FO	Median
11	FO	RobustMeanAbsoluteDeviation
12	FO	RootMeanSquared
13	FO	Skewness
14	FO	TotalEnergy
15	FO	Uniformity
16	GLCM	ClusterProminence
17	GLCM	ClusterShade
18	GLCM	ClusterTendency
19	GLCM	Correlation
20	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
21	GLCM	DifferenceEntropy
22	GLCM	Id
23	GLCM	Idm
24	GLCM	Idmn
25	GLCM	Idn
26	GLCM	Imc1
27	GLCM	Imc2
28	GLCM	InverseVariance
29	GLCM	JointEnergy
30	GLCM	JointEntropy
31	GLCM	MaximumProbability
32	GLCM	SumEntropy
33	GLDM	DependenceEntropy
34	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformity
35	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformityNormalized
36	GLDM	DependenceVariance
37	GLDM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
38	GLDM	LargeDependenceEmphasis
39	GLDM	LargeDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
40	GLDM	LargeDependenceLowGrayLevelEmphasis
41	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
42	GLDM	SmallDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
43	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
44	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
45	GLRLM	LongRunEmphasis
46	GLRLM	LongRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
47	GLRLM	LongRunLowGrayLevelEmphasis
48	GLRLM	RunEntropy
49	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
50	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformityNormalized
51	GLRLM	RunPercentage
52	GLRLM	RunVariance
53	GLRLM	ShortRunEmphasis
54	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
55	GLSZM	LargeAreaEmphasis
56	GLSZM	LargeAreaHighGrayLevelEmphasis
57	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
58	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
59	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
60	GLSZM	ZoneEntropy
61	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
62	GLSZM	ZoneVariance
63	NGTDM	Busyness
64	NGTDM	Coarseness
65	NGTDM	Contrast
66	NGTDM	Strength

Virtual Monoenergetic Reconstructions

Features with High Agreement and Reliability

Average High CCC Ratio: 51.0%

Average High ICC Ratio: 56.0%

Average Number of High CCC Features: 46

Average Number of High ICC Features: 50

Table S30 – Analysis results of average values of radiomic features extracted from virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

Study	Comparison Case	High_CCC	High_CCC_No	High_ICC	High_ICC_No
Agreement and Reliability	100 keV	50.55%	46/91	56.04%	51/91
Agreement and Reliability	110 keV	50.55%	46/91	54.95%	50/91
Agreement and Reliability	120 keV	50.55%	46/91	54.95%	50/91
Agreement and Reliability	130 keV	50.55%	46/91	54.95%	50/91
Agreement and Reliability	140 keV	50.55%	46/91	54.95%	50/91
Agreement and Reliability	150 keV	50.55%	46/91	54.95%	50/91
Agreement and Reliability	160 keV	50.55%	46/91	54.95%	50/91
Agreement and Reliability	170 keV	50.55%	46/91	54.95%	50/91
Agreement and Reliability	180 keV	50.55%	46/91	54.95%	50/91
Agreement and Reliability	190 keV	50.55%	46/91	54.95%	50/91
Agreement and Reliability	40 keV	51.65%	47/91	58.24%	53/91
Agreement and Reliability	50 keV	51.65%	47/91	58.24%	53/91
Agreement and Reliability	60 keV	51.65%	47/91	58.24%	53/91
Agreement and Reliability	70 keV	51.65%	47/91	57.14%	52/91
Agreement and Reliability	80 keV	51.65%	47/91	56.04%	51/91
Agreement and Reliability	90 keV	51.65%	47/91	57.14%	52/91

Figure S18 – Analysis results of the average values of radiomic features extracted from virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

Feature Classes with High Agreement

Figure S19 – Feature classes with high agreement in analysis of the average values of radiomic features extracted from virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

Feature Classes with High Reliability

Figure S20 – Feature classes with high reliability in analysis of the average values of radiomic features extracted from virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

Names of Features with High Agreement

Table S31 – Feature names with high agreement in analysis of the average values of radiomic features extracted from virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	90Percentile
2	FO	Energy
3	FO	Entropy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	RootMeanSquared
6	FO	Skewness
7	FO	TotalEnergy
8	FO	Uniformity
9	GLCM	Correlation
10	GLCM	DifferenceEntropy
11	GLCM	Id
12	GLCM	Idm
13	GLCM	Idn
14	GLCM	Imc1
15	GLCM	Imc2
16	GLCM	InverseVariance
17	GLCM	JointEnergy
18	GLCM	JointEntropy
19	GLCM	MaximumProbability
20	GLCM	SumEntropy
21	GLDM	DependenceEntropy
22	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformity
23	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformityNormalized
24	GLDM	DependenceVariance
25	GLDM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
26	GLDM	LargeDependenceEmphasis
27	GLDM	LargeDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
28	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
29	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
30	GLRLM	LongRunEmphasis
31	GLRLM	LongRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
32	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
33	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformityNormalized
34	GLRLM	RunPercentage
35	GLRLM	RunVariance
36	GLRLM	ShortRunEmphasis
37	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
38	GLSZM	LargeAreaHighGrayLevelEmphasis
39	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
40	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
41	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
42	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
43	NGTDM	Busyness
44	NGTDM	Coarseness
45	NGTDM	Strength

Names of Features with High Reliability

Table S32 – Feature names with high reliability in analysis of the average values of radiomic features extracted from virtual monoenergetic reconstructions in test and retest scans, before and after rotation of phantoms

No.	Feature Class	Feature Name
1	FO	90Percentile
2	FO	Energy
3	FO	Entropy
4	FO	Mean
5	FO	Median
6	FO	RootMeanSquared
7	FO	Skewness
8	FO	TotalEnergy
9	FO	Uniformity
10	GLCM	Correlation
11	GLCM	DifferenceAverage
12	GLCM	DifferenceEntropy
13	GLCM	Id
14	GLCM	Idm
15	GLCM	Idn
16	GLCM	Imc1
17	GLCM	Imc2
18	GLCM	InverseVariance
19	GLCM	JointEnergy
20	GLCM	JointEntropy
21	GLCM	MaximumProbability
22	GLCM	SumEntropy
23	GLDM	DependenceEntropy
24	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformity
25	GLDM	DependenceNonUniformityNormalized
26	GLDM	DependenceVariance
27	GLDM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
28	GLDM	LargeDependenceEmphasis
29	GLDM	LargeDependenceHighGrayLevelEmphasis
30	GLDM	SmallDependenceEmphasis
31	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
32	GLRLM	GrayLevelNonUniformityNormalized
33	GLRLM	LongRunEmphasis
34	GLRLM	LongRunHighGrayLevelEmphasis
35	GLRLM	RunEntropy
36	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformity
37	GLRLM	RunLengthNonUniformityNormalized
38	GLRLM	RunPercentage
39	GLRLM	RunVariance
40	GLRLM	ShortRunEmphasis
41	GLSZM	GrayLevelNonUniformity
42	GLSZM	LargeAreaHighGrayLevelEmphasis
43	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformity
44	GLSZM	SizeZoneNonUniformityNormalized
45	GLSZM	SmallAreaEmphasis
46	GLSZM	ZoneEntropy
47	GLSZM	ZonePercentage
48	NGTDM	Busyness
49	NGTDM	Coarseness
50	NGTDM	Strength

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